

Campus Universitário de Almada
Instituto Superior de Estudos Interculturais e Transdisciplinares

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Intensity of physical education classes and its relationship with recommendations for children's physical activity in this context

Licenciatura em Educação Física e Desporto

Orientador Interno: Professora Doutora Denise Paschoal Soares

Orientador Externo: Professor Carlos Claro

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Relatório final de estágio apresentado com vista à obtenção do grau de Licenciado em Educação Física e Desporto (1º ciclo de estudos) ao abrigo do Aviso n.º 9930/2017 de 28 de agosto de 2017

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We received your manuscript and thank you for choosing to publish in JPES. I will send this article to the reviewers team and then I will notify the selected authors about the acceptance decision.

Due to the large volume of correspondence we will not be able to answer everyone and we apologize for this.

Other details of the publication process will be sent ONLY to these selected authors.

Thank you

Resumo

A educação física (EF) tem sido considerada como um cenário ideal para promover níveis mais elevados de intensidade moderados a vigorosos (MVPA) nos jovens. A recomendação para aulas de educação física (REF) em crianças com intensidade MVPA é de pelo menos 50% do tempo total de aula. Após o confinamento obrigatório devido à pandemia covid-19, foram implementadas regras restritas pelo governo, que afetaram as aulas de EF. É importante compreender como todas estas consequências afetam a atividade física das crianças (AF) nas aulas de EF. O objetivo deste estudo é avaliar a intensidade das aulas de EF nos vários ciclos de escolaridade e verificar se as crianças conseguem atingir as REF para esta população. A amostra foi constituída por 301 alunos (1º até ao 12º ano) que foram avaliados em aulas de EF com diferentes tipologias e duração. A intensidade foi avaliada através de um acelerómetro. Os dados foram agrupados em dois níveis de intensidade, o sedentário/leve (SEDLV) e o moderado a vigoroso (MVPA) cada em tempo (h:m:s) e em percentagem (%). Descobriu-se que no 2º ciclo, as meninas passavam mais tempo na intensidade MVPA. Outra constatação é que a aula de 2 horas no 3º ciclo apenas duplicou o tempo sedentário/leve (SEDLV) em vez do tempo MVPA. Mostrou-se que as aulas politemáticas promovem mais tempo ao nível MVPA em vez de classes unitemáticas. Em relação à percentagem de tempo de AF, 31% a 43% do tempo total da aula foi no nível MVPA. Conclui-se que as crianças e jovens passam muito tempo na intensidade SEDLV, o que pode levar a problemas futuros e piorar a saúde das crianças. É crucial implementar estratégias que se centrem no tempo em MVPA nas aulas de EF e reduzir o tempo morto entre as atividades.

Palavras-chave: *crianças, acelerometria, saúde, covid-19, sedentarismo*

Abstract

Physical education (PE) has been considered as an ideal setting for promoting higher moderate to vigorous (MVPA) levels in youth. The physical education recommendation (PER) for children in MVPA intensity is at least 50% of total class time. After the mandatory lockdown due to the covid-19 pandemic, strict rules were implemented by the government, which affected PE classes. It is important to understand how all these consequences affect children's physical activity (PA) in PE classes. The aim of this study is to evaluate the intensity of PE classes in the various scholar cycles and verify if children achieve PER for this population. The sample consisted of 301 students (1st till the 12th grade) who were evaluated in PE classes with different tipology and durations. Intensity was assessed using accelerometry. Data were grouped in two intensity levels sedentary/light (SEDLI) and moderate to vigorous (MVPA) each in time (h:m:s) and in percentage (%). It was found that in 2nd cycle, girls spent more time in MVPA intensity. Other finding is that 2-hour class in 3rd cycle only doubled sedentary/light time (SEDLI) instead of MVPA time. It was found that polythematic classes promote more time in MVPA level rather than unithematic classes. In relation to intensity during the class, 31% to 43% of class total time were in MVPA level. It is concluded that children spent a lot of time in SEDLI intensity, which can lead to future problems and worsen children's health. It is crucial to implement strategies that are focused on increasing MVPA time in PE classes and reduce dead time between activities.

Key Words: *children, accelerometry, health, covid-19, sedentarism*

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Introduction

Before the covid-19 pandemic, young people spent on average 9 hours/day in sedentary behaviors, excluding sleep time (Lopes et al., 2015). In addition, only 36% of children and adolescents between 15 and 21 years were considered physically active (Lopes et al., 2015). In relation to physical education (PE) classes, only one third of time were devoted to vigorous activity (Fairclough & Stratton, 2005; Viciano et al., 2015), which demonstrates the lack of physical activity (PA) and brings numerous consequences such as increased risk of obesity, cardiovascular problems, diabetes, and all causes of mortality, including cancer (Mattioli et al., 2020). There seem to be different activity levels amongst the youth, as youngest children up to 9 years (68%) are more active than adolescents between 10 to 14 years (57%) (Lopes et al., 2015)

With the covid-19 pandemic, changes in diet, sleep and lack of regular PA aggravated. Indeed, studies have shown a physical activity decrease of 2,3 hours per week among children and adolescents (Pietrobelli et al., 2020). During confinement, about 80% of the time of children under 12 years old, was spent in sedentary behavior (Pombo et al., 2020), being most of the time spent in front of the screen due to mandatory confinement with online classes.

After the lockdown, when activities became presential again, in relation to PE classes, there was a higher incidence of rules to be complied defined by the government (Conselho de Ministros, 2020) prepared by the Health General Board (DGS, 2020) elaborating a guidance document that implies a adopting preventive measures such as: using outdoor spaces instead of interiors; to provide strategies and methodologies that respect the physical distance of at least 3 meters, to adapt the tasks to this aspect; to avoid the sharing of material among students, without being sanitized between usage and to repeat the content that requires recovery/consolidation.

It becomes essential to know how pandemic and, consequently, the rules-imposed affect PE classes.

Particularly, PE, due to its compulsory character, has been considered as an ideal setting for promoting higher moderate to vigorous intensity (MVPA) levels in youth (WHO, 2008). Its main objective is to promote opportunities to practice PA, making students physically fit and to give them tools to develop a physically active and healthy lifestyle (Lin et al., 2019; Pate et al., 2006)

The physical education recommendation (PER) for children in MVPA intensity is at least 50% of total class time available (Association for Physical Education, 2015). Studies show that in days with PE classes, children are more active comparing to non-PE days (Mayorga-Vega et al., 2018; Viciano et al., 2017), demonstrating that PE can enhance MVPA time. However, low motivation or sensibilization exacerbates the lack of interest, reducing the practice of PA in the school context. Consequently, PE represents a good chance to achieve higher activity levels and thus contributing to children's health (Department of Health and Human Services, 2008; Sierra-díaz et al., 2019).

Accelerometers are objective instruments with easy application to all age groups (Fabre et al., 2020; Trost, 2013) and that has been used frequently over the years to measure physical activity in different contexts (Troiano, 2005).

In the school environment, the PE classes have already been evaluated previously with accelerometers, showing to be a valid instrument and easy application, because it does not interfere in the realization of classes and presents important results about intensities in the classes of PE (Mayorga-Vega et al., 2018; Viciano et al., 2017). Other studies conducted in the pre-pandemic context show that PE classes reach 33% of the recommended time (Fairclough & Stratton, 2005). Besides that, this moment there is no knowledge of any study that have evaluated PE classes intensity in this post lockdown context.

It is important to understand whether all these consequences and changes, children who returned to presential classes after an extended period of confinement, can reach recommended intensities and promote an improvement in their physical conditions by achieving, through these, the recommendations of daily PA for PE classes.

Thus, considering the importance of a study of the intensity of PE classes and their relationship with PER for children in this new context, the aim of this study is to evaluate the intensity of physical education classes in the various scholar cycles and verify if children achieve PER for this population.

Material & method

Participants

The sample consisted of 301 students from the 1st until the 12th grade, where 1st grade includes 4 scholar years (1st to 4th), 2nd grade includes 2 years (5th and 6th), 3rd grade includes 3 years (7th, 8th, 9th) and High School that includes 3 years (10th, 11th, 12th) shown in Table 1 .

Table 1 - Characterization of the sample according to gender, age, height, and body mass

Scholar Cycles	Gender (n)	Age Years old [range]	Height cm (sd)	Body Mass Kg (sd)
1st cycle	Male (56)	[6 to 9]	1.33 (0.10)	30.68 (7.60)
	Female (62)		1.29 (0.10)	27.48 (5.08)
2nd cycle	Male (17)	[10 to 12]	1.43 (0.67)	37.28 (7.19)
	Female (12)		1.48 (0.09)	39.18 (8.16)
3rd cycle	Male (12)	[13 to 15]	1.65 (0.09)	54.16 (8.66)
	Female (17)		1.59 (0.05)	49.32 (6.61)
High School	Male (11)	[16 to 18]	1.77 (0.06)	63.91 (10.43)
	Female (9)		1.71 (0.04)	54.76 (4.79)

Procedures

Firstly, an authorization was signed from the school board to authorize the development of the study, followed by an informed consent form sent to children's legal guardians. The research was approved by the Ethics Committee under the number CEIP/3/2020 (submission date: Oct 1st, 2020; approval: Nov 4th, 2020).

A form of each class was filled out to discriminate ID of child (i.e., subject 1 - accelerometer 1); the duration of the class (divided in 1-hour and 2-hour classes by scholar year); the type of class (work by stations/circuits with multiactivity – polythematic or unithematic with only 1 sport approached).

Regarding the 1 and 2-hour classes, the distribution of the sample in class duration were that 1st grade has 100% 1-hour, 2nd grade has 100% 2-hour, 3rd grade has 70% 2-hour and 30% 1-hour and high school has 100% 1-hour.

Data collection was done during the school's regular PE classes, where accelerometers were placed on the children before the beginning of class, to not interfere with the functioning or duration of the class.

Instruments

For the evaluation of body composition, the Bioimpedance Equipment Inbody 270 (InBody USA, Cerritos, CA, USA) was used, which, through the transmission of an electrical impulse through the body, determines the body composition of the subject. Height was measured with the Seca station (GmbH & Co, Hamburg, Germany)

The intensity of PE classes was measured with the accelerometer ActiGraph wGT3X + BT (Pensacola, FL, USA) sensitive to movements performed up to 8g of magnitude ($1g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$) used during all classes in the non-dominant wrist. The setup of the accelerometers was done at a frequency of 60Hz, with a setup during all week counting the classes daily for posterior analysis using a time filter to define a PE class time to each class.

Data Processing

Data were downloaded at a 5sec epoch length to be applied later the following cut-off values (units in counts/min): Sedentary < 305, Light 306-817, Moderate 818-1968, Vigorous >1969 (Chandler et al., 2015). The common approach of accelerometry data in PE classes is computing the total time spent in MVPA intensity to determine active or inactive activity (Aibar & Chanal, 2015) so data are presented grouping sedentary and light intensities (SEDLI) and moderate to vigorous (MVPA) intensity.

The time in minutes at each intensity was calculated using the Program Actilife (v 6.13.4), in which a time filter was also applied between the start and end time of each class, performed according to the information filled out in the class form.

Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics version 27.0 software. First, the normality of the distribution as well as the homogeneity of variances were verified. A t-test was used for independent samples to compare the time spent in each intensity between gender, 1h and 2h classes and classes tipology; One-way anova test was performed to compare the intensity of classes among scholar years. Where anova revealed significant interactions, data were further studied using a post-hoc Tukey's b. The level of significance was set to $p < 0.05$.

Results

No significant differences were found between gender in relation to the time spent in each intensity applied in the classes (Table 2) in the 1st, 3rd and high school cycle year between genders,

In relation to the 2nd cycle, significant differences were found between genders for sedentary and light (SEDLI) intensity level ($p=0.037$), with the male gender spending more time in this intensity, and to moderate and vigorous intensity (MVPA) level ($p = 0.037$), with female gender spending more time in this level.

Regarding the 3rd cycle and high school, no significant differences were obtained for any intensity level.

Table 2 – Comparisons between genders according to % time spent in each intensity grouped by scholar cycle

Scholar Cycle	Gender	SEDLI		MVPA	
		% total class time	P value	% total class time	P value
		Mean (sd)		Mean (sd)	
1 st cycle	M	55.92 (14.11)	0.270	44.01 (14.11)	0.270
	F	58.04 (14.45)		41.96 (14.45)	
2 nd cycle	M	73.23 (7.84)	0.037*	26.77 (7.84)	0.037*
	F	66.96 (7.64)		33.04 (7.64)	
3 rd cycle	M	61.46 (2.76)	0.824	38.54 (2.76)	0.824
	F	60.37 (10.98)		39.63 (10.98)	
High School	M	67.67 (5.40)	0.258	31.33 (5.40)	0.258
	F	70.85 (6.77)		29.15 (6.77)	

Legend: M – male; F – female; SEDLI – sedentary and light intensity; MVPA – moderate to vigorous intensity; % SEDLI plus % MVPA represents 100% total class time

Since only the 3rd cycle had classes of 1 and 2-hour, figure 1* shows the differences between these classes, were there was significant difference in time spent for intensity SEDLI ($p = 0.003$) and MVPA levels ($p=0.003$).

Only the 1st cycle had classes of two types of the work by stations/circuits with multiactivity – polythematic and unithematic with only 1 sport approached. Figure 1# shows the differences between these two types with statistical significance for SEDLI ($p=0.001$) and MVPA levels ($p=0.001$)

Figure 1 – Comparison between 1h and 2h classes and classes typology for 3rd and 1st grade respectively (* - significant differences between 1h and 2h classes; # - significant differences between classes typology)

The relation between time spent in each intensity level and scholar cycles is shown in figure 2. The 1st cycle spent an average of 25 minutes (43%) of 1-hour total time in MVPA intensity, 2nd cycle 35 minutes (29%) of 2-hour total time in MVPA, 3rd grade 23 minutes (39%) of 1-hour total time in MVPA and 34 minutes (29%) in 2-hour total time in MVPA and high school 18 minutes (31%) in MVPA. Among scholar years, in 2-hour classes there were significant differences between 1st and 2nd cycle ($p < 0.01$) and between 1st and 3rd cycle ($p < 0.001$). In 1-hour class, there were significant differences between 1st cycle and high school ($p = 0.001$).

Figure 2 – Time spent in each intensity of physical activity according to scholar cycle. In 3rd cycle, the classes were divided into one hour and 2h duration; * shows significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the intensity of physical education classes in the various scholar cycles and relate these levels with the PER for this population.

To this end, classes of different typology and duration were evaluated for all years grouped by scholar cycles.

Comparisons about percentage of time spent in each intensity between genders according to grouped by scholar cycle, showed significant differences in 2nd cycle, with girls spending more time in MVPA intensity ($p=0.037$). Previous studies showed that boys are more active than girls (Howells & Coppinger, 2021; Rooney & McKee, 2018; Silva et al., 2015), although in single gender classes, girls present more time in MVPA intensity than in mixed-gender classes (Wallace et al., 2020). In this study, the classes were mix-gender type. Even though a probable explanation for 2nd cycle girls being more active can be due to the school's culture with a great amount sports offer available, other study showed that these offer promotes higher PA levels in afterschool programs (Kuritz et al., 2020).

Surprisingly, comparisons between 1h and 2h classes in 3rd cycle showed significant differences in percentage of time spent in each intensity, where children spent 39% of 1-hour class in MVPA contrary to 2-hour class, where they spent 29% of total time in MVPA ($p=0.003$). The recommendation is to spend 50-80% of PE class available time in a moderate to vigorous intensity (Association for Physical Education, 2015). In our study it is shown that promoting more time for PE above 1-hour could lead to a double of the time in SEDLI level instead of the time in MVPA that was supposed to increase. These results indicate that the extra time of the class is spent in transition time, explanations and not in MVPA activities. Teachers should adopt strategies to improve efficiency (Grube et al., 2018) and increase practice time.

Between classes typology in 1st grade there were significant differences for both SEDLI and MVPA intensity ($p=0.001$). The higher offer of stimulus related to a polythematic class provides more motivation for students (Metzler, 2011). Also, in this typology, children spent less time in only one sport, promoting the contact with different sports in the same class (Vieira, 2015).

According to the time spent in each intensity level and scholar cycles, it is demonstrated that 1st cycle reached about 43% of total time class in MVPA intensity, 2nd and 3rd cycles (2-hour class) appear to be 29% in MVPA intensity and 1-hour class from 3rd cycle, 39% was in MVPA intensity. In high school, only 31% of total time was in MVPA intensity. This demonstrates that younger children spent more time in MVPA intensity, and it tends to decrease with aging. These results were also demonstrated in other study (Pulido Sánchez & Iglesias Gallego, 2021), which showed that as children grow, levels of physical activity tend to decline, where the youngest people perform the greatest MVPA.

Regarding to the influence of the adaptations related to covid-19 pandemic, our study shows with different approaches and classes duration that children are below the recommended percent of time for this age. Strategies should be taken into consideration for promoting a higher level of MVPA intensity being this a goal to achieve along with developing appropriate skills, knowledge and understanding to children optimize their physical activity opportunities (Fairclough & Stratton, 2005)

This study has some limitations such as not all scholar cycles had the chance to get the two classes typology and for the 1-hour and 2-hour class that would be the ideal sample. However, these results show that children, despite the tendency to decrease levels of physical activity with aging, do not reach the recommended values during PE classes, noting that 2-hour classes only increase time at low intensities and cannot promote time in MVPA intensity. It is extremely important to find strategies during classes that promote longer practice time and reduce wasted time in explanations or transition between activities so that children could spend most of the time available in practice.

Conclusions

Children spent most of the time in SEDLI intensity during PE classes, which can lead to future problems and worsen children's health. It is crucial to implement strategies that are focused on increasing children MVPA time in PE classes and reduce dead time between activities. Two-hour classes only double SEDLI time instead of promoting more time in MVPA intensity. Girls were more active than boys in this study, and polythematic classes is a good strategy to increase the offer of stimulus and motivate children to do more. It is crucial to increase scientific knowledge and get solutions with the purpose of improving children's health and promote healthy lifestyles.

Conflicts of interest - no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Anexo I –Requerimento ao Colégio para Autorização do Estudo

Requerimento

Nós, Catarina Filipa Costa Rodrigues e Joana Filipa Dias Silva Lourenço, estagiárias do Colégio Atlântico no âmbito da disciplina de Prática de Ensino de Educação Física, solicitamos ao diretor do Colégio, Dr António Pereira, autorização para pedir consentimento aos pais, de autorização para participação no estudo que pretendemos desenvolver como parte do relatório final. A avaliação consiste na monitorização da atividade física diária dos alunos e a sua influência na saúde. Estes dados irão ser tratados através de variáveis diferentes, como a comparação entre géneros e a prática ou não de atividade física extracurricular, sendo estas informações adquiridas através de um inquérito a ser respondido pelos mesmos. Para que tal seja feito, agradecemos que nos desse acesso aos dados antropométricos (idade, peso, altura) das turmas 6º A e 6º B em observação, de modo a prosseguir com o caso de estudo. Os resultados serão confidenciais e os nomes dos alunos não serão revelados.

Atenciosamente,

Catarina Rodrigues e Joana Lourenço.

(Estagiárias de Educação Física do Colégio Atlântico)

Assinatura das estagiárias:

Catarina Rodrigues

Joana Filipa Lourenço

Assinatura da Coordenadora Interna do Instituto Piaget de Almada:

Luís

Assinatura do Diretor do Colégio Atlântico:

António Pereira

Data: 3/11/2020

Termo de consentimento esclarecido

Exmo. Sr. Encarregado de Educação,

Vimos por este meio informá-los que os alunos do Colégio Atlântico, Participarão de um estudo intitulado COVID ACTIVE, que tem por objetivo avaliar a intensidade das aulas de Educação Física no contexto de pandemia. A avaliação consistirá na recolha de dados antropométricos (idade, peso, altura) e na monitorização da intensidade das aulas de Educação Física, com o objetivo de determinar se os níveis de atividade física estão de acordo com o recomendado. Estes dados irão ser adquiridos através de um inquérito, a ser respondido pelos alunos, a respeito das atividades realizadas fora do período escolar. Posteriormente, cada aluno utilizará um pequeno equipamento, do tamanho de um relógio, que irá medir o gasto calórico durante sua utilização e que nós iremos disponibilizar, para ser usado durante a aula de Educação Física. Os resultados serão confidenciais e os nomes dos alunos não serão revelados.

Quaisquer questões adicionais queiram, por favor, contactar a docente responsável desta pesquisa:

Denise P. Soares E-mail: denise.soares@almada.ipiaget.pt Telemóvel: 915805660

Estagiárias:

Catarina Rodrigues E-mail: catarinafiliparodrigues@hotmail.com Telemóvel: 960331789

Joana Lourenço E-mail: joana.fds16@gmail.com Telemóvel: 927979895.

Anexo III – Parecer da Comissão de Ética

Parecer da Comissão de Ética do Instituto Piaget (n.º 3/2020)

Título do Projeto: Análise do comportamento motor e aptidão física de crianças e adolescentes em idade pré-escolar e escolar.

Nome do responsável do projeto: Denise Soares (KinesioLab)

Breve Descrição: Este projeto de investigação em educação física decorrerá em contexto escolar, tendo como objetivo avaliar o comportamento motor de crianças e adolescentes em idade pré-escolar e escolar. Os participantes (Crianças em idade escolar) serão avaliados em relação à sua aptidão física, competência motora, aprendizagem motora e coordenação motora. As avaliações serão feitas em ambiente escolar, com a devida autorização do diretor da escola e um consentimento informado dos pais. Realce-se que não foi determinado qualquer risco potencial, nem desconforto para nenhum dos participantes. Os participantes têm a oportunidade de abandonar o projeto a qualquer momento, bastando para tal informar o professor responsável pela investigação. É garantido que o abandono do projeto não terá qualquer consequência para o(a) aluno nem para os seus encarregados de educação.

Parecer da comissão: Depois de analisar a documentação entregue pelo responsável deste projeto, a Comissão de Ética do Instituto Piaget emite um parecer favorável, confirmando que este está dentro dos princípios éticos que devem nortear a investigação científica.

4 de novembro de 2020, Vila Nova De Gaia

Pela Comissão Científica,

(Professor Doutor Luís Moreira)

(Professor Doutor Hélder Pinto)

(Professor Doutor José Luís Sousa)